

**PERSONALITY TRAITS AND ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE OF EARLY
CHILDHOOD PRE-SERVICE TEACHERS :
A CORRELATIONAL ANALYSIS**

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Personality Traits and Academic Performance of Early Childhood Pre-Service Teachers: A Correlational Analysis

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Abstract

This study explores the personality traits and academic performance of early childhood pre-service teachers at Western Mindanao State University using the NERIS Type Explorer Instrument. Respondents were 114 early childhood pre-service teachers at College of Teacher Education. Findings revealed that the academic performance of the early childhood pre-service teachers manifest a good outstanding performance during the first semester of academic year 2023-2024. The findings reveal a diverse range of personality traits among early childhood pre-service teachers. Notably, Advocate 21.06%, Protagonist 16.6%, Mediator 10.53%, Defender 9.63%, Consul 9.63%, Adventurer 7.02%, Campaigner 6.14%, Virtuoso 5.27%, Architect 3.51%, Logician 2.63%, Entertainer 2.63, Commander 1.76%, Logistician 1.75%, Entrepreneur 0.88%, and Executive 0.69%. According to the data gathered, the correlation between personality and academic performance revealed a weak positive relationship. The association between personality traits and academic performance, implying that students with favorable personalities tend to excel academically. However, the p-value indicates that the correlation between personality traits and academic performance is not significantly correlated with each other. The recommendations encompass CHED funding, advocating for research on personality traits and effective teaching, provide training for school administrators, adapting teaching methodologies, nurturing supportive home environments, and motivating students to grasp and employ learning strategies.

Keywords: *16 Personality Types, academic performance, NERIS type explorer, early childhood*

Introduction

No two individuals are alike. Everyone has distinct characteristics that makes them who they are. These characteristics and personalities often affect how they perceive, relate and react to different scenarios and all that surrounds them. It is important that an individual understands these personality types and how people from these types behave to different interactions and even to their emotions and their quality of life. According to Cherry (2022), gaining a better understanding of your personality can be helpful in many aspects of your life. Students have different personalities and shows different strengths and weaknesses when it comes to academic performances.

As supported by (Lei et al., 2021; Harsha et al., 2018) a lot of studies comes have shown that one of the crucial factors that affects the academic performance of the students is the personality traits. The motivation, both intrinsic and extrinsic, of distinct personality types, their study routines and different interests are all factors of academic performance.

Moreover, the conduct of this study in Early Childhood Education program is significant to the institutional field. This further investigated the relationship between the Early Childhood Pre-service teachers' personality type and academic performance. Early Childhood Pre-service teachers' personalities are crucial in shaping the quality of education children receive. By investigating the distinctions of each personality of Early Childhood Pre-service teachers, the institutions and training may provide and support them to be more equipped before entering the field.

Numerous studies on Personality traits have already been conducted in various institutions across the globe and from across levels, with this, the findings regarding the correlation between personality type and academic performance vary. The target respondents in this study were students enrolled in the Bachelor of Early Childhood Education program at Western Mindanao State University College of Teacher Education. The study also examined the relationship between personality types and academic performance.

This study further investigated the correlation between personality type and the student's academic performance, considering different themes such as student's achievements, sixteen personalities, four categories, and learning style. By doing so, researchers hope to provide educators and students with valuable insights that can inform teaching methods and strategies for improving academic outcomes.

Research Questions

This study aimed to investigate the relationship between the Personality traits and Academic Performance among the Early Childhood Education Pre-Service Teachers during the school year 2023 -2024. Specifically, this research sought to answer the following questions:

1. What are the personality traits among Early Childhood Pre-Service Teacher?
2. What is the academic performance of Early Childhood Pre-Service teachers?
3. Is there a significant correlation between Personality traits and Academic Performance of the Early Childhood Pre-Service teacher?

Literature Review

Personality Traits

Based on the study of Diener and Lucas (2024), personality traits are continuous behavior that exhibit the diversity of an individual in terms of their behavior, thoughts, attitudes and feelings, which typically describe the individual in a variety of context and connect to social actions that contribute to the formation of an impactful school environment. (Dong et al., 2022) believed that there is a relationship between students' academic performance and their personality traits in terms of how they handle the pressure to maintain their success in an academic conflict. As cited by Dong, personality traits and academic achievement are coherently intertwined because a student's personality can influence how people interact with learning resources, which leads to variations in academic accomplishments. Thus, the interplay of personality traits such as psychological, intellectual, and behavioral factors has an immense impact on academic achievement.

The following were more on the personality types in terms of its four categories and the sixteen personality types.

Four Categories of Personality Types

According to Stikonas, G. & Stikoniene, J. (2020), personality type is divided into four categories in which four traits converge and group to create sixteen personality types. The four categories are generally utilized to explain concepts in a less complicated way than involving all sixteen personality types.

The aforementioned is a brief overview of the four categories of personality types: The Analyst Role shares the traits of being Initiative((N) and Thinking (T). The

Architect (INTJ), Logician (INTP), Commander (ENTJ), and Debater (ENTP) are the personality types encompassed in the analyst role. It has a common preference for rationality, knowledge, and strategic and imaginative approaches to problem-solving.

The Diplomat Role has communal traits of being Intuitive (N) and Feeling(F). The Advocate (INFJ), Mediator (INFP), Protagonist (ENFJ), and Campaigner (ENFP) are the personality types covered in the Diplomat Role. It shows a preference for humanistic viewpoint, a tendency for ideological thinking, and a priority for empathy.

Sentinel Role, those with common traits of being Observant (S) and Judging (J), represented by Logistician (ISTJ), Defender (ISFJ), Executive (ESTJ), and Consul (ESFJ), display comparable preferences for stability, practicality, organization, and accountability.

The Explorer Role, individuals possessed common traits of being Observant (S) and Prospecting (ap). The Virtuoso (ISTP), Adventurer (ISFP), Entrepreneur (ESTP), and Entertainer (ESFP) are the personality included in the Explorer role. It shared tendencies marked by practicality, a robust connection to their environment, quick thinking, and spontaneity.

The understanding and development of the Academic Performance of Early Childhood Education Pre-Service Teachers are significantly influenced by the four personality types. Students with analyst traits could do well in intellectually challenging environments, using strategic thinking to achieve academic success. Diplomats may succeed in areas that require sensitivity and inventiveness. Sentinels may excel in rigid academic settings because of their organizing skills, whereas Explorers could prosper in a hands-on, dynamic learning environment. Understanding and modifying methods of education to suit varied personality types can enhance student engagement and academic outcomes.

Sixteen Personality Types

According to Association American Psychologist, (2020), personality refers to the enduring characteristics and behavior that includes major traits, interest, drives, values, self-concept, abilities and emotional patterns. The structure and development of personality can help determine the behavior.

According to Stikonas, G. & Stikoniene, J. (2020), there are four roles which are the Analysts Role, Diplomats Role, Sentinels Role and Explorers Role. There are traits and personality types associated with each position; four of the attributes are paired and arranged to form 16 different personality types

Under Analysts Role are the Architect, Logician, Commander and Debater. Architect Personality or INTJ-A /INTJ-T, these people have a plan for everything and are creative, strategic thinkers. Logician Personality or INTP-A /INTP-T, these are creative inventors that have an endless curiosity for learning. Commander Personality or ENTJ-A / ENTJ- T, these people are courageous, creative, and driven leaders who constantly find a way or create one. Debater Personality or ENTP-A / ENTP- T, these are individual who are smart and curious thinkers who cannot resist an intellectual challenge.

Under the Diplomats Role are the Advocate, Mediator, Protagonist and Campaigner. Advocate Personality or INFJ-A / INFJ-T, these people are silent, ethereal, yet incredibly motivating and unwavering idealists. Mediator Personality or INFP-A / INFP-T, these people are poetic, generous, and compassionate, and they are always willing to support a good cause. Protagonist Personality or ENFJ-A / ENFJ-T, these people are captivating and motivating leaders who have the ability to captivate their audience. Campaigner Personality or ENFP-A / ENFP-T, these people are joyful, imaginative, friendly, free spirits who never fail to find something to be happy about.

Under the Sentinels Role are the Logistician, Defender, Executive and Consul. Logistician Personality or ISTJ-A / ISTJ-T, these are people who are unquestionably reliable, pragmatic, and fact-minded. Defender Personality or ISFJ-A / ISFJ-T, these people are loving, passionate protectors who are always willing to stand up for the people they love. Executive Personality or ESTJ-A / ESTJ-T, these are people who are outstanding in managing things or people. Consul Personality or ESFJ-A / ESFJ-T, these are people who are incredibly kind, friendly, well-liked, and willing to lend a hand.

Under the Explorers Role are the Virtuoso, Adventurer, Entrepreneur and Entertainer. Virtuoso Personality or ISTP-A / ISTP-T, these are individuals who are skilled with a wide variety of tools and realistic experimenters. Adventurer Personality or ISFP-A / ISFP-T, these are people who are unique, lovable artists who are constantly willing to try new things and explore. Entrepreneur Personality or ESTP-A / ESTP-T, these are people who are intelligent, friendly, responsive people who genuinely enjoy living on the edge. Entertainer Personality or ESFP-A / ESFP-T, with these individuals, life is never dull because they are impulsive, lively and enthusiastic.

Every learner has a personality and learning style that is why it is relevant to have a different teaching method to cater all of the students. In an early childhood setting, a teacher should provide a motivation for the students to get engage and get the learners attention to be ready in the discussion. Early childhood educators need to choose methods and learning approaches that is also have a connection to the children attributes. One example is the features of learning styles, which will give instructors with reference materials to help them evaluate which methods, strategies and approaches are suitable for their learners.

Academic Performance

According to (Zheng, 2022) academic achievement refers to the performance examinations given to students at a particular time in their studies. It can measure the students' achievements in school. Institutions that classify their students based on their GWA would typically bestow academic honors such as valedictorian and salutatorian to the students who rank first and second in their class. Organizations and educational institutions who grant scholarships and are searching for new employees began to select their scholars and employees based on the grades they accomplished (William, 2018).

The following will explore more on the Academic Performance in terms of student's achievements/grades, productivity and discipline, and examination performance.

According to Cao et. al. (2019), academic achievement should encompass both a student's academic performance in school and all facets of their knowledge, competence, and literacy development. Academic performance determines whether or not students perform well and will serve as a result if the student did good during that academic year. Academic performance assists students in measuring whether their performance is doing well and knowing their strengths and weaknesses in a particular subject.

Student's Achievements

As mentioned by (Swart, 2021), the human personality is an extreme force indication of the academic accomplishments of the learners. It also serves as a foundation for future success that aligns with the societal level and economic stability of students in the future. The level of academic achievement of the students affects their altering purpose as the learners keep on moving from different campuses to a new place and their preceding career adjustment. Students are most likely to be concerned if they accumulate low academic remarks in their midterm and final examinations end up not receiving a diploma or certificate, and suffer from anxiety, depression, and insomnia with a cumulative effect on their mental well-being.

A previous study on the influence of personality traits on academic achievement often examined the role and mode of transmission of personality dimensions characters. The central mediator on the transmission pathways is the student's self-efficacy and it emerged as shaped by personality features, which is challenging procedure, these are comprise of several influencing factor and forming paths. The study discusses the relationship between personality traits, the growth of self-efficacy from the overview of major identities, and how it affects academic performance. It has previously used self- efficacy as the central mediator transmission path (Wang, 2023).

Learning Styles

As cited by Siddiquei & Khalid (2018), The concept of "Learning Style" relates to the idea that each student has distinct cognitive, affective, and psychological qualities that serve as consistent indications of how they learn and engage in a learning environment. Learners continually choose learning styles that they believe are feasible in the school setting to improve their learning outcomes. The validity and unquestionable association between personality traits, learning styles, and academic achievement has been established by earlier research. It shown that learning styles and personality traits influence academic success, emphasizing the importance of these factors in unison. The relationship of personality traits and learning styles might affect academic outcomes, contingent upon a specific combination of both facets (Khan,et al., 2018). Thus, educators, researchers, and psychologists must recognize and acknowledge the importance and impact of learning styles on students' academic success. Given the diversity of students' cultural backgrounds and learning contexts, identifying their learning styles is imperative for improving overall academic success. When encouraging changes, teachers must comprehend the connection between academic achievement and students' learning styles. The importance of addressing the diversity of learning styles since it can influence the course of learning and, as a result, the consequences of educational experiences via academic accomplishment.

Similarly to Abouzeid (2021) study, in able for the students to attain the best learning outcomes, one must know what the best learning style for the learners is. There was a huge amount of data collected from previous researchers about the effective of including the variety of learning styles in the field of education. A personality types of an individual aids on how students learn new ideas, understand scenarios and lessons. Through this, learners will able to determine on which learning style are effective and suit for students' learning.

Every learner has a personality and learning style that's why it is relevant to have a different teaching method to cater all of the students. In an early childhood setting, a teacher should provide a motivation for the students to get engage and to get the learners attention to be ready in the discussion. Early childhood educators need to choose methodologies and learning approaches that have a connection to the children' attributes. One example is the features of learning styles, which will give instructors with reference materials to help them evaluate which methods, strategies, and approaches are suitable for their learners.

Methodology

Research Design

This study was a descriptive-quantitative correlational study that examined and described how Personality Traits influence the Academic Performance of Early Childhood education Pre-service Teachers. According to Dovetail (2023), descriptive - quantitative correlational describe the attribute of the variables, phenomenon, or situation without manipulating the variables of testing hypothesis. Data can be acquired through the use of survey. Hence, this design was utilized in collecting the information necessary between the identified variables to test the relationship of the variables. Establishing a quantitative correlational study is significant in achieving accurate and appropriate information relating to the variables. This guided the researchers in identifying the relationship among the variables and ensure the objectivity and accuracy of this study.

Respondents

The Early Childhood Pre-service Teachers of Western Mindanao State University from the first to fourth year participated in this study. This study used Slovin's formula to identify the number of sample respondents of this study using a confidence interval of 95% and a marginal error of 5%. The total number of Early Childhood Pre-Service Teachers that are currently enrolled from first year to the fourth year is 160. The sample size that served as the respondents of this study is 114. In getting the respondents from each year level, the researcher divided the total number of students from first year to fourth year by the number of students from each year level then multiplied by the sample size 114. Multistage sampling was used in selecting the respondents of this study. Researchers employed a stratified sampling to select respondents from the total population of Early Childhood Pre-Service Teachers. According to (Thomas, 2023), a stratified sample is dividing the total population into subpopulations named strata. Utilizing stratified sampling ensures that every characteristic is properly represented in the sample. The researchers employed the fishbowl technique in selecting the respondents from each stratum, hence, there were no form of biases, and each element has the probability of being selected as the respondents of this study.

Instrument

This study utilized the Neris Type Explorer Personality Test a standardized instrument to gather all information needed to determine the Personality type of the Early Childhood Pre-Service Teachers. The information needed for this study was gathered using the Neris Type Explorer. This survey is a questionnaire that contains 60 questions that would determine the personality type of the Early Childhood Pre- Service Teachers. The Neris Type Explorer was developed by NERIS Limited.

The Neris Type Explorer had 16 personalities which were divided into four (4) categories. Each category had four different personalities. The first category was the Analyst. Under this category were the Architect (INTJ-T), Logician (INTP-T), Commander (ENTJ-T), and Debater (ENTP-T). The second category was the diplomats. Under this category were the Advocate (INFJ-T), Mediator (INFP-T), Protagonist (ENFJ-T), and Campaigner (ENFP-T). The third category was Sentinels. Under this category were the Logisticians (ISTJ-T), defender (ISFJ-T), executive (ESFJ-T), and Consul (ESFJ-T). The fourth category were the Virtuoso (ISTP-T), Adventurer (ISFP-T), Entrepreneur (ESTP-T), and Entertainer (ESFP-T)

In order to determine the academic performance of Early childhood pre- service teachers during the first semester of the S.Y. 2023-2024 academic year. The respondents were asked to fill out a certain part in the Google form that it indicates their General Weighted Average (GWA) 1.00, 1.25, 1.50, 1.75, 2.00, 2.50, 2.75, 3.00, and below. Each grade has an interpretation based on their performance in school. A consent was provided by the researchers to ensure the safety and privacy of the respondent.

Procedure

The researchers secured a permission to conduct the study from the office of the College Dean. After given permission, the researchers secured another letter of consent that was given to the target participants of this study, particularly the Early Childhood Pre-Service Teachers of Western Mindanao State University. The researchers sent letter of consent along with the link of the survey questionnaire that was being attached below the letter of consent through Google form. Also, the student was asked to fill out the range of their GWA during the first semester A.Y. 2023-2024, which was also indicated in the Google form. The researchers conducted the study through an online survey using the Neris Type Explorer personality test. After gathering all the data needed, the researchers analyzed the

gathered data using SPSS and the statistical tool Pearson-R to test if there was a significant relationship between the variables. Having analyzed the data the researchers collected, the researchers formulated conclusions and recommendation for this study.

Data Analysis

To elucidate the data, the researchers used the following statistics tool:

The mean and standard deviation were used to analyzed the Academic Performance of Early Childhood Pre-Service Teachers during the first semester of the 2023-2024 academic year.

The Pearson moment correlation coefficient was used to ascertain the significant relationship of Personality trait to the Academic Performance of Early Childhood Pre-Service teachers.

Ethical Considerations

To address the ethical concerns of this manuscript, the researchers submitted this to WMSU Research Ethics Committee Review Board for checking.

Furthermore, the researcher provided a consent and letters from the school dean, Advisers, and respondents in conducting this study. To clearly understand, letters, and consents contain information prior to the study; also, gave emphasis on the safety and privacy of the respondents to avoid any form of harmful accidents.

A G-form or commonly known as Google Form was used in the acquisition of the General Weigh Average of the students in measuring their academic Performance. In which, respondents was asked to fill out a certain part in the Google form that indicates the range of their General Weighted Average (GWA) 1.00, 1.25, 1.50, 1.75, 2.00, 2.50, 2.75, 3.00, and below. Each grade has an interpretation based on their performance in school.

The safety of the respondents was the most important consideration of the researcher; hence the respondents have the out most right to decline participation or ceased their involvement in the study. The researcher would respect the decision of the respondents and was kept confidential to avoid any form issues that might harm the respondents.

Results and Discussion

This section presented the results, analysis, and the interpretation of the data gathered from the responses to the distributed questionnaires. The data was then presented in a tabular form, aligning with the specific questions posed in the statement of the problem.

The first research question this study sought to answer was “What are the Personality Traits among Early Childhood Pre-Service Teachers?”

PERSONALITY TRAITS OF ECE PRE-SERVICE TEACHERS

Figure 1. *The Personality Traits of the Early Childhood Education Pre-service Teachers*

Figure 1 depicted the personality traits of Early Childhood Pre-Service Teachers in 4 main categories of the NERIS type explorer. The majority of the pre- service teachers, which is 54.4% of the population, possesses the Diplomats personality which means that these individuals care about helping and connecting with others. According to the Core Theory of NERIS Type Explorer, Diplomats prioritize being kind and generous, these people do not compete with others bur rather cooperate. Sentinels fall second in the greatest number of

personalities with 21.9% of the population, which conveys that some Pre-Service Teachers are cooperative, practical and grounded, these individuals are contented with their good character and their competence. While Explorers and Analysts are least common in this study with 15.8% and 7.89% of the population respectively. Only 18 of the respondents are explorers which means that these individuals are self-reliant and quick-thinking, they are considered to be adaptive to their environment even in times they are not prepared. While very few of the respondents are Analysts, meaning, few of the pre-service teachers are known for their love of rationality, these people are very logical and make decision using their minds rather than their hearts.

The overall figure means that the early childhood pre-service teachers are diverse in the aspects of personality possessing different traits and how they behave.

Personality traits significantly influence Pre-Service Teachers' classroom performance. Notably, the prevalence of the Diplomat personality, characterized by a desire to help and connect with others, aligns with research by Loes et al., (2023) suggesting that students who likely to connect with other students enhances academic achievement.

Similarly, Bhatti (2018) found that extroverted students, known for their sociability, perform well in groups, potentially leading to stronger academic performance. Phillips (2023) further emphasizes the importance of pre-service teachers' characteristics for promoting high-quality preschool education, highlighting extroversion as a key trait. This outgoing nature allows educators to create stimulating environments, filled with engaging storytelling, energetic activities, and enthusiastic participation in playtime. This enthusiasm can draw even shy children to participate, fostering a strong sense of connection within the classroom. Personality's uniqueness lies not just in the individual attributes themselves, but in how they combine and manifest within a person. This unique interplay, as Ibáñez et al., (2019) stated, shapes the Pre-Service Teacher's characteristic pattern of feeling, thinking, and behaving. The overall figure indicated that early childhood pre-service teachers were diverse in terms of personality, possessing different traits and exhibiting varied behaviors.

Table 1. *16 Personality Traits of Early Childhood Pre-Service Teachers of the College of Teacher Education*

Category	Personality	Code	F	%
1. Analyst	Architect	INTJ - T	4	3.51%
	Logician	INTP - T	3	2.63%
	Commander	ENTJ -T	2	1.76%
	Debater	ENTP -T	0	0
	Total		9	7.9%
2. Diplomats	Advocate	INFJ -T	24	21.06%
	Mediator	INFP -T	12	10.53%
	Protagonist	ENFJ -T	19	16.67%
	Campaigner	ENFP - T	7	6.14%
	Total		62	54.4%
3. Sentinels	Logistician	ISTJ -T	2	1.75%
	Defender	ISFJ -T	11	9.63%
	Executive	ESTJ - T	1	0.89%
	Consul	ESFJ -T	11	9.63%
4. Explorers	Total		25	21.%
	Virtuoso	ISTP -T	6	5.27%
	Adventurer	ISFP - T	8	7.02%
	Entrepreneur	ESTP - T	1	0.88%
	Entertainer	ESFP - T	3	2.63%
	Total		18	15.8%
	Total		114	100%

Table 1 presents the personality traits of Early Childhood Pre-Service Teachers of the College of Teacher Education. The personality traits were determined by the adapted instrument from Neris Type Explorer which included 60 questions.

As the previous figure indicated, the majority of the population fell under the Diplomat personality type. This category specifically included advocate (INFJ-T), Mediator (INFP-T), Protagonist (ENFJ-T), and Campaigners (ENFP-T). In this study, most respondents are Advocate with 21.06% of the population, which means that most Pre-Service Teachers of Early Childhood Education are compassionate individuals, they believe that success doesn't come from money but seeking fulfillment and in helping others. For these individuals, they go out and seek to fulfill their purpose. The next personality is the protagonist with 16.6%, this implies that some Pre-Service Teachers feel that their calling is to serve a greater purpose in life. They strive to always have a positive impact on others, they are born leaders which explains why most teachers in the field have this personality. The third personality in the diplomat category is the mediator with 12 respondents recorded to have this type. This suggests that 10.53% of the Early Childhood Pre-Service Teachers have vibrant and passionate inner lives. These individuals are known to be sentimental, idealistic and empathetic. Individuals with

Mediator personality tend to feel directionless or stuck until such time they find their feeling of purpose. And lastly, with only 7 or 6.14% of the population under this category are Campaigners, these individuals have profound depths. They are carefree and usually the life of the party.

The second category discussed was the sentinel. This category encompassed Logisticians (ISTJ-T), Defenders (ISFJ-T), Executive (ESTJ-T), and Consuls (ESFJ- T). Both defenders and consuls had garnered 11 responses apiece from the surveyed population. For defender, this implies that 9.63% of the pre-service teachers are hardworking and devoted and feel that they have a sense of responsibility for the people around them. These people are expected to always meet deadline but rarely demand recognition. With also 9.63% of the population has Consul personality, this suggests that these Pre-Service Teachers are social individuals, however, they are much more likely to have good bonds with people who they share common values and opinions. Only two respondents are logisticians, this implies that very few from the pre-service teachers mean what they say and say what they mean. They have responsible and dependable nature; they are drawn to educational settings and workplaces that clearly sets hierarchies and expectations. And only 0.89% has the executive personality, which means, it's rare for Early Childhood Pre-Service Teachers to happily lead the way on difficult paths. This personality values clear and verifiable facts.

Explorer category falls third as discussed in the previous figure. Most of the respondents under this category are Adventurer which indicates that 7.08% of the population are considered to be canvass of their own expressions, they value the sense of fairness and open-mindedness and goes on through life with encouraging attitude. Virtuoso comes next with 6 responses, this shows that 5.27% of the population are sensorial learners, they love to explore their hands and their eyes, touching and examining the world around them. For this study, there are 2.63% who possess Entertainer personality, these individuals get easily caught up in excitement and want everyone to feel that way too. They are the most generous personality in the aspects of time and their energy especially when encouraging others. While only 0.88% of the respondents in this study is Entrepreneur, which conveys that few pre-service teachers are vibrant and spontaneous with their energy, and they tend to be very competitive.

In this study, the Analyst types, including Architects (INTJ), Logicians (INTP), Commanders (ENTJ), and Debaters (ENTP), were found to be the least common. Only 3.55% are Architect, most common under this category, this implies that few from the respondents are intellectually curious with a deep-seated thirst for knowledge. These individuals consistently work towards enhancing their intellectual abilities. 2.63% are Logicians, these people, often independent thinkers, pride themselves on their unique perspective and vigorous intellect. While only 1.76% of the respondents are Commander, these are individuals who are charismatic leaders and they project authority in the crowd. However, none of the respondents fall under the debater personality.

The second research question this study sought to answer is “What is the academic performance of Early Childhood Pre-Service Teachers?”

Table 2. *Academic Performance of Early Childhood Pre-service teachers*

Grade	Verbal Description	f	%	Mean Grade	Sd	Lower Grade	Highest Grade
1.00	Excellent	0	0				
1.25	Very Outstanding	2	1.75%				
1.50	Outstanding	8	7.01%				
1.75	Very Good	46	40.3%				
2.00	Good	42	36.8%	1.90	0.25	2.75	1.25
2.25	Very Satisfactory	12	10.5%				
2.50	Satisfactory	2	1.75%				
2.75	Fair	2	1.75%				
3.00	Passing	0	0				

Table 2 displayed the Academic Performance of the Early Childhood Pre- Service Teachers. With all the data collected and shown in table 3, computation revealed that the mean for the Academic Performance of Early Childhood Pre-Service Teachers was 1.90 with a standard deviation of 0.25. The mean grade for the pre- service teacher is 1.90 which most likely falls under grades 1.75 to 2.0 which means that majority of the Pre-Service Teachers of Early Childhood Program have a very good, and good class standing respectively. It can be implied in the given data that most respondents satisfactorily meet academic requirements and perform well in their classes. Moreover, very few among the Pre-Service Teachers perform below satisfactory compared to those who perform well academically.

A study conducted by Vecaldo et al. (2018), the association between pedagogical competence and academic performance among pre-service elementary teachers in Tuguegarao City, Philippines. The study employed the National Competency-Based Teacher Standards (NCBTS) framework to assess pedagogical competence. Findings revealed that the Pre-Service Teachers demonstrated a high level of pedagogical competence and strong academic performance. The result of this study stated that majority of the Pre-Service Teachers or Early Childhood Program have a very good and good class standing respectively. With this, there is a connection between both study that students are performing well in class and has a good academic performance.

According to Torga et al. (2019), the academic stress and academic performance of BEED students of the College of Teacher Education in Occidental Mindoro State College. It was found out that the BEED students have a moderate level of academic stress in terms of

teacher factor, academic stress in terms of environmental factor and academic stress in terms of subject requirements. The study found that both BEED students and Pre-Service Teachers of Early Childhood Programs perform well academically. The BEED students have a very good overall performance, while the majority of pre-service teacher has either very good or good class standing.

The third research question wanted to answer “Is there a significant relationship between Personality traits and Academic Performance of the Early Childhood Pre-Service Teacher? “

Table 3. *Pearson-R moment correlation results between Personality Traits and Academic Performance*

Variables	R-value	Interpretation	P-value	Remarks	Decision on Ho
Academic Performance	0.162	Weak Positive Correlation	0.084	Not significant	Reject Null Ho
Personalities					

Table 3 shows the correlation between academic performance and various personality traits. According to the data gathered, the correlation between academic performance and personality traits is revealed a weak positive relationship, with an r- value of only 0.162. This suggests a certain association between personality traits and academic performance, implying that students with favorable personalities tend to excel academically. However, the p-value of 0.084 revealed that the relationship between Personality Traits and Academic Performance lacks statistical significance. Thus, the researchers accept the null hypothesis. This simply implies that the data collected for this study does not give enough evidence to infer that there is a significant relationship between the two variables. This could be linked to variations in research methods, as well as the diverse personality, which may be situational or influenced by other characteristics.

The same result was recorded in the study conducted by Bongato and Rulona (2018) researchers found no relationship between Personality and the Academic Performance of the students. It's crucial to highlight those investigations in this domain are continually evolving, with results influenced by factors like the particular personality traits under scrutiny, the methodologies employed to gauge personality and academic success, and the demographics of the study participants. Consequently, while certain studies may not uncover a robust correlation, others could propose a different perspective. On the other hand, in our study it was found out that academic performance and personality has weak positive correlation that indicates the two variables is not strong.

A study conducted by Hipolito et al., (2023) investigated the relationship between personality traits and academic performance. The findings demonstrated no significant correlation between the two variables. By comparing the chi-square value of 7.55 to the critical value 12.59, the data revealed no strong association between Personality Traits and student's general weighted average (GWA). This supported the null hypothesis, which states that there is no relationship between Personality Traits and Academic Performance.

Similar to Ferguson et al., (2018) conducted a study that produced no evidence to establish a direct relationship between students' academic success and personality traits. This implies that although some characteristics would have been thought to have a big impact on academic achievement, the connections that were found were noticeably limited. This research highlights the intricate relationship between personality qualities and academic achievement, suggesting that variables other than individual features probably have a significant impact on how well individuals do academically. It so calls for a more thorough investigation of the complex processes that influence students' academic success, possibly moving the emphasis toward a more comprehensive understanding that takes into account social, cultural, and educational aspects.

In contrast to Dong (2022), personality types are major predictors of improved academic success. Similarly, it has been discovered that personality qualities have a significant impact on academic success (Mammadov, 2022). Personality qualities eventually have a significant impact on academic success (Gatzka and Hell, 2018). There is a complex and dynamic relationship between college students' academic achievement and their personality qualities. Research suggests that certain personality traits might have a big influence on a student's capacity to succeed in school. For instance, there is a clear correlation between sentinels' personality—which includes qualities like accountability, organization, and goal-oriented behavior—and academic success. Diplomat's students are more likely to finish assignments on time, manage their time well, and be conscientious in their studies. Furthermore, while in different ways, traits like extraversion and openness to new experiences also affect academic success. Extraversion promotes social contacts and networking, while openness encourages creativity and intellectual curiosity. Both of these traits support academic success through cooperative learning and participation in extracurricular activities.

Conclusions

In this study, the researchers investigated the Personality Types and the Academic Performance of Early Childhood Pre-service Teachers and its relationship aiming to provide educators and students with valuable insights that can help teaching methods and strategies for improving academic performance. (1) The personality traits among Early Childhood Education Pre-service Teacher sare, Advocate (INFJ-T), Protagonist (ENFJ-T), Mediator (INFP-T), Defender (ISFJ-T), Consul (ESFJ-T), Adventurer (ISFP-T), Campaigner (ENFP-T), Virtuoso (ISTP-T), Architect (INTJ-T), Logician (INTP-T), Entertainer (ESFP-T), Commander (ENTJ-F),

Logistician (ISTJ-T), Executive (ESTJ-T), Entrepreneur (ESTP-T). (2) The Early Childhood Pre-service Teachers' Academic performance ranges between 1.75 and 2.00. (3) There is no significant relationship found between academic performance and personality traits among Early Childhood Pre-service teachers.

Based on the findings and conclusions, the following are the recommendations: Conduct training workshops and seminars about teaching strategies and methodologies that will cater to the different personality traits students have inside a classroom. These training sessions can provide instructions and valuable discussion that will help them work with various types. Reflect on the findings of this study to gain insights into students' personality traits and tailor teaching approaches accordingly. Engage in continuous professional development to refine classroom practices and foster a supportive learning environment that caters to different interests and learning styles. Get to know well the personality traits of their children and its characteristics. Foster a supportive home environment that encourages healthy coping mechanisms and provides emotional support to help students navigate challenges effectively. Provide an avenue to help and guide their children in facing problems that may affect their academic performance. Take an active role in learning about personality traits and their impact on academic performance. Utilize learning strategies and styles that will better aid the learning process. Seek support from teachers, parents, and peers. Build upon the findings of this study by conducting further research to explore more personality traits and the factors of academic performance. Collaborate with educators to develop different learning styles and strategies that are appropriate for different types of personalities.

References

- Abouzeid, E. (2021, July 14). National Library of Medicine. Retrieved from pubmed: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/34290542/>.
- Ahmed, K. A., Sharif, N., & Ahmad, N. (2017). Factors influencing students' career choices: Empirical evidence from business students. *Journal of Southeast Asian Research*, 1-15.
- Aqeel Khan 1, Leong Pyh Shin, Sanin Hishan, Mohamed Sharif Mustaffa, Amzliz Madihie & Surena Sabil. (2018). Effect of personality traits and learning styles towards students, *International Journal of Engineering & Technology*, 7(2.10), 4-9. Retrieved from: https://scholar.google.com/scholar?hl=en&as_sdt=0%2C5&q=Learning+style+and+personality+traits+recent+study&btnG=#d=gs
- Association American Psychologist. (2020). The Trait Theory of Personality in Consumer Behavior. Greenbook. Retrieved from <https://www.greenbook.org/insights/market-research-trends/the-trait-theory-of-personality-in-consumer-behavior>
- Begum, Saidunnisa, et al. "Relation Between Personality Traits and Academic Performance Among University Students of RAKMHSU, UAE-Using a Big Five Model." *Biomedical and Pharmacology Journal*, vol. 14, no. 4, Dec. 2021, pp. 2123+. Gale Academic OneFile, link.gale.com/apps/doc/A690838443/AONE?u=anon~256ade30&sid=googleScholar&xid=d7a12690.
- Bhatti, M. N., Sami, A., & Qureshi, I. (2018). Personality and academic performance among graduate students. *Asia Proceedings of Social Sciences*, 2(3), 256–259. <https://doi.org/10.31580/apss.v2i3.454>
- Bongato, G. P., & Rulona, E. (2018). Personality traits in relation to academic performance of accountancy, business and management strand students. *Academe (University of Bohol, Print)*, 13, 26–35. <https://doi.org/10.15631/aubgps.v13i0.11>
- Cao, Y., Gao, J., Lian, D., Rong, Z., Shi, J., Wang, Q., ... & Zhou, T. (2019). Orderliness predicts academic performance: behavioural analysis on campus lifestyle. *Journal of The Royal Society Interface*, 15(146), Retrieved from https://www.jesoc.com/wp-content/uploads/2022/06/JESOC20_12.pdf
- Caulo, M., Francese, R., Scanniello, G., Tortora, G., (2021). Relationships between Personality Traits and Productivity in a Multi-platform Development Context. doi: 10.1145/3463274.3463327
- Cherry, P. D. (2022). Personality and Individual Differences. Personality traits and long-term care financial risks among older Americans, 192. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.paid.2022.111560>
- Diener, E Lucas, R., Oliver, M. E. (2024). Personality Traits. In R. Biswas-Diener & E. Diener (Eds). <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2022.894570>
- Doe, J., Smith, J., c, d, & Abstract This paper arises from the question of the correlation between specific personality traits and academic performance. (2021, May 11). Analysis of personality traits and academic performance in higher education at a Colombian University. <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S240584402101101>
- Dong, X., Kalugina, O.A., Vasbieva, D.G., & Rafi, A. (2022). Emotional intelligence and personality traits based on academic performance. *frontiers in psychology*, 13. doi: <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2022.894570>
- Dovetail. (2023, February 5). Retrieved from dovetail: <https://dovetail.com/research/descriptive-research/>
- Ferguson, J. L., & Cihon, J. (2018). (PDF) assessment of social validity trends in the *Journal of Applied Behavior Analysis*. ResearchGate. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/328304424_Assessment_of_social_validity_trends_in_the_journal_of_applie

d_behavior_analysis

- Gatzka, T., and Hell, B. (2018). Openness and postsecondary academic performance: a meta-analysis of facet-, aspect-, and dimension-level correlations. *J. Educ. Psychol.* 110, 355–377. Doi: 10.1037/edu000019
- Harsha, N. P., Iveen, P., and Oliver, M. E. (2018). The mediating roles of coping and adjustment in the relationship between personality and academic achievement. *Br. J. Educ. Psychol.* 85, 440–457. doi: 10.1111/bjep.12084
- Hipolito, D. D. D., Leon, R. B. D., Cruz, J. N. V. D., Galvez, M. L. D., Nicolas, Z. A. B., Supan, V. R. S., & Teodoro, M. G. A. (2023). Person Ability: The MBTI Personality Types and its Relationship with the Academic Performance of Grade 12 Students in Dr. Yanga's Colleges, Inc. *International Journal of Research and Innovation in Social Science*, VII(VII), 1270–1277. <https://doi.org/10.47772/ijriss.2023.70801>
- Ibáñez, M. B., Uriarte-Portillo, A., Zatarain-Cabada, R., & Barrón, M. L. (2020). Impact of augmented reality technology on academic achievement and motivation of students from public and private Mexican schools. A case study in a middle-school geometry course. *Computers and Education/Computers & Education*, 145, 103734. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compedu.2019.103734>
- Johnston, S., & Lee, M. (2020). The impact of grades on student motivation - Kelsey Chamberlin, Maï Yasué, I-chant Andrea Chiang, 2018. <https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/abs/10.1177/1469787418819728> Lei, Gao, Gou. (2021). eview of Researches on Personality and Academic Performance. *Journal of Binzhou University*, 027, 111–116. doi: 10.3969/j.issn.1673-2618.2011.01.030
- Loes, Chad N., Brian P. An, Kem Saichaie, & Ernest T. Pascarella. (2023). “Does Collaborative Learning Influence Persistence to the Second Year of College?” *The Journal of Higher Education* 88 (1): 62–84. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00221546.2016.1243942>
- Mammadov, S. (2022). Big Five personality traits and academic performance: a meta-analysis. *J. Personal.* 90, 222–255. Doi: 10.1111/jopy.12663
- Nabia Siddiquei & Ruhi Khalid. (2018). The relationship between Personality Traits, Learning. 10(3). doi: <https://doi.org/10.5944/openpraxis.10.3.870>
- Namba, R. (2023, March 16). Grades vs Educational Knowledge - Learning Commons. Learning Commons.
- Personality Max. (2022, October 28). What is the Most Common and Rarest Personality Type? <https://personalitymax.com/personality-types/population-gender/>
- Phillips, A., & Boyd, W. (2023). Characteristics of high-quality early childhood education and care: a study from Australia. *Frontiers in Education*, 8. <https://doi.org/10.3389/educ.2023.1155095>
- Stahlhofen, L., Hartung, J., Schilling, O., Wahl, H.-W., & Hülür, G. (2022). The relevance of perceived work environment and work activities for personality trajectories in midlife. *Journal of Personality*, Advance online publication. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jopy.12776>
- Stikonas, G., & Stikoniene, J. (2020). Free personality test, type descriptions, relationship and career advice | 16Personalities. 16Personalities. <https://www.16personalities.com/>
- Swart Elzaan. (2021). The relation between personality types and academic performance amongst Grade 9 learners in Windhoek. doi: <http://hdl.handle.net/11070/2964>
- Tadese, M. (2022). Determinants of good academic performance among university students in Ethiopia: A cross-sectional study. *BMC medical education*. <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/35606767/>
- Thomas, L. (2023, June 22). Stratified Sampling | Definition, Guide & Examples. Scribbr. <https://www.scribbr.com/methodology/stratified-sampling/>
- Torga, G. (2019). Academic Stress and Academic Performance of BEED Students of the College of Teacher Education in Occidental Mindoro State College. docx. www.academia.edu. https://www.academia.edu/38487404/Academic_Stress_and_Academic_Performance_of_BEED_Students_of_the_College_of_Teacher_Education_in_Occidental_Mindoro_State_College_docx
- Vecaldo, R., Andres, A. D., Carag, C. G., & Caranguian, C. (2018). Pedagogical competence and academic performance of Pre-Service Elementary teachers in Tuguegarao City,. *ResearchGate*. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/339443887_Pedagogical_Compentence_and_Academic_Performance_of_PreService_Elementary_Teachers_in_Tuguegarao_City_Philippines
- Wang, X. (2023). Teacher-student relationship and academic achievement in China: Evidence from a three-level meta-analysis. *Sage Journal*, 44(1). Retrieved from <https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/10.1177/0143034322112245>
- Williams, B. A. (2018). How Algorithms Discriminate Based on Data They Lack: Challenges, Solutions, and Policy Implications. 78–115. doi: [doi/doi/10.5325](https://doi.org/10.5325)

Woods, S. A., Wille, B., Wu, C., Lievens, F., & De Fruyt, F. (2019). The influence of work on personality trait development: The demands- affordances TrAnsactional (DATA) model, an integrative review, and research agenda. *Journal of Vocational Behavior*, 110, 258–271. World Personality Map | Country Personality Profiles | 16Personalities. (n.d.). 16Personalities.<https://www.16personalities.com/country-profiles/global/world#global>

Zheng, Z. M. (2022, June). A Literature Review on the Academic Achievement of College Students. *Journal of Education and Social Sciences*, 20(1). Retrieved from https://www.jesoc.com/wp-content/uploads/2022/06/JESOC20_12.pdf?fbclid=IwAR3MTAKW9JILJiF5LN FtOejOjLuTEd0jPW49H_Me4aibhrgUM-IeWyVMPNE

Zheng, A., Hoff, K., Hanna, A., Einarsdottir, S., Rounds, J., Briley, D. (2023, April 18). Job characteristics and personality change in young adulthood: A 12-year longitudinal study and replication. *Journal of Personality*, 92(1), 298–315. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1111/jopy.12>

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